

Nurses' Role in Healthcare Quality Improvement

Dhaidan Abdullah Almutairi¹, Ahmed Abdullah R Alosilan², Majed Abdullah Alotaibi³, Mona Mutlaq K Almutairi⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Majmaah University

ABSTRACT

Introduction: In addition to nursing, the nurse gives the patient medical attention by giving injections and managing medications. She helps the physician with diagnosis and therapy. The advancement of technology and rising demands for health care have changed the meaning of this profession. Nursing models that emphasize the practical application of learned information demonstrate the evolution of this profession. The purpose of this study was to outline the responsibilities, skills, and role of the nursing profession in raising the standard of patient care.

Material and method: The literature analysis method is used in this work. The information utilized in the work is derived from scientific journals and publications that have been released in compressed form.

Results: The analysis of the gathered scientific data demonstrated that nurses have a major influence on both the standard of medical care and the smooth operation of the entire institution. Healthcare facilities are part of organizations where a patient's life and health are directly impacted by the quality of care provided. As a result, everyone on staff should prioritize the patient's care, especially the nurses who spend a lot of time getting to know them and meeting them first. Patients look to nurses for medical expertise above all else, but they also expect safety, trust, and appropriate communication.

Conclusions: The nursing field has seen significant change in recent years, necessitating a variety of actions from those working in it to advance their careers. Additionally, patient expectations are evolving. Success depends on getting their feedback and meeting their needs. A happy customer will undoubtedly employ the facility's services once more.

KEYWORD: nursing; quality of care; patient

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
10 October 2024

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

INTRODUCTION

The autonomous medical profession includes the profession of nursing. A nurse plays a critical role in the therapeutic team, performing numerous duties that allow for increased public access to healthcare. Nursing is always changing, assuming new responsibilities and skills to keep up with patients' rising demands. A person having the necessary credentials, which he obtained during his study, and the authorization to practice the profession can perform this job. The Act on Professions of Nurse and Midwifery provides a detailed description of the regulations governing the practice of the profession, acquiring permission to practice, and professional and post-graduate training. Nurses can take part in a variety of training programs and specialized courses to increase their skills [1,2].

Nurses' tasks

The goal of nursing is to support people in realizing their full potential—mental, physical, and social—in the settings in which they live and work every day. The purpose and core values of the nursing profession directly inform the duties performed by nurses. Its main responsibilities include planning nursing interventions, evaluating patient requirements, and identifying which duties call for the assistance of other experts in related fields [3]. A nurse's duties also include keeping track of completed tasks so that they can be more effectively scheduled in the future. Respecting the relevant ethical, cultural, and professional standards is also involved. Activities aimed at promoting health and preventing disease involve identifying, evaluating, and stopping any actions that endanger life or health [4]. A proactive role is played by nurses in the execution of health

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initiatives. They provide nursing care, teach patients about leading healthy lives, and tend to the sick. They are crucial in helping patients get ready for self-care whether they are unwell or disabled. They play a significant role in the groups of individuals who develop health policies and take part in research initiatives [5].

A nurse's work primarily entails the following tasks:

- identifying the health and nursing needs of patients;
- organizing all care activities;
- offering preventative, diagnostic, therapeutic, and rehabilitation services independently within the parameters of their training
- carrying out a doctor's suggestions
- Selecting the kind of benefits
- Endorsing initiatives for health promotion and prevention
- educating patients about health;
- leading nursing research;
- supervising teams of nurses and midwives;
- conducting ongoing professional development activities

The development of the nursing profession is a process that arises from the ongoing need to provide the best care possible for both the youngest groups of people and the elderly participation in the teaching of the medical professions, if provided for in the training program conducting administrative work consisting in the organization and supervision of individual health services [6]. It is insufficient to just concentrate on providing for the patient's medical needs. The World Health Organization places a strong emphasis on recognizing people as bio-psychosocial entities and realizing the roles that biological, psychological, and social variables play in both the development of disease and promoting health. Patients' expectations of medical professionals are rising because of the dynamic nature of human health and the need to meet their requirements [7, 8].

Defining the profession according to nursing models

Creating nursing models that attest to the profession's practical and scientific advancement is the solution to patients' wants and issues. There have also been modifications to the definition of nursing itself [9].

The creator of contemporary nursing, Florence Nightingale, created a community nursing approach. She said that in addition to medical expertise, a nurse should be knowledgeable in statistics, administration, public health, law, and ethics. She thought that because of the enormous influence that humans have on the environment, they may enhance their health by changing it. The benefits of this model's assumptions can only be realized with the participation of all medical professionals and by utilizing the body of information from related sciences [10].

The Hildegard Peplau interpersonal relationship model defines a nurse as an individual who carries out his or her professional responsibilities in relation to patient therapy in order to restore the patient's health. She teaches the patient self-control techniques, problem-solving techniques, and

how to overcome her fears and worries about the illness. This paradigm emphasizes the multidisciplinary nature of the nursing profession because, in addition to medical expertise, education or psychological knowledge is also required [11].

The use of the Virginia Henderson paradigm is the assistance given to both ill and well individuals. The author thought that in order to provide the greatest care possible for a patient, a nurse should continuously enhance her skills. The International Council of Nurses has accepted her definition of nursing as universally applicable. Maslow's theory of needs forms the basis of this concept. The nurse's job is to ensure that the patient gains independence as quickly as possible and doesn't require assistance with everyday tasks. [12].

One of Dorothy Ormen's other models highlights that nursing is a social service that involves providing care for those who are unable to do it for themselves for a variety of reasons. She made a distinction between nursing systems, self-care deficiency theory, and self-care theory in her paradigm. The capacity for self-care is influenced by a number of variables, including family dynamics, age, gender, and health. Every human being engages in self-care to guarantee the optimal circumstances for preserving health. When someone requires nursing care because they are unable to satisfy their own requirements, such as due to disease, they are said to have a self-care deficit. The patient might occasionally be able to complete certain tasks on his own, but he could lack the necessary skills or drive. This calls for the application of a nursing system known as support and education, which entails giving this individual the information he needs in a way that is appropriate for his skills and assisting him with all of his activities. We are discussing a fully compensating system when the patient needs assistance with every task, or a partially compensating system when the assistance is only partial [13, 14].

The adaptive nursing model's inventor, Callisa Roy, asserts that nursing integrates practical and scientific elements. Identifying adaptive reactions should be a priority of nursing activity. The nurse's job is to get the patient ready for a life that has been turned upside down by the illness. Adapting the family to changes is also crucial [15].

Every nursing care model that has been offered places an emphasis on the profession's accountability and the real-world application of learned skills. Providing the greatest care possible to both the ill and the well is their primary objective. This support ought to extend to the mental as well as the physical domains [16].

The challenges and professional responsibilities that nurses encounter are strongly linked to the advancement of knowledge. Nurses and scientists studying biology, psychology, social work, philosophy, economics, and other fields that include management and guidance theory collaborate closely. Multidisciplinary work is crucial because it enables accurate patient need identification and efficient analysis [17, 18].

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Quality in health care

In order to give patients, the best treatment possible, it is crucial to keep an eye on their requirements. The word "quality" is used a lot in the modern world, both in publications and in daily life. This phrase has been around since antiquity. These days, there are many different definitions of quality, and it mostly relies on the context [19]. Quality is an activity that complies with regulations and is designed to meet market demands. The phrase refers to the process of carrying out a product or service in a way that satisfies clients. Several explanations for the phrase exist, each taking into consideration the unique characteristics of a certain market. The alterations result in a quality customer. indication, at least mostly. Quality encompasses all of the related activities in addition to the features of a particular process or product. Without a question, improving quality should be the primary goal of any modern organization, particularly in the case of medical facilities [20].

In order to be categorized as service activities, medical services must include a few fundamental characteristics. The first is immateriality, since patients cannot predict how their therapy will turn out in advance of seeing their physician. Inescapability is the second characteristic. Medical services are provided concurrently to patients and staff; they cannot occur in their absence. In order to effectively achieve the stated aim of better health, it is also crucial to involve the patient in the treatment process [21]. Additionally, the medical service is irreversible. This implies that after a specified deadline passes, it cannot be used. Another characteristic is diversity, which denotes that each patient is a unique case, necessitating that medical professionals modify each patient's diagnosis and course of therapy [22].

Because it has a direct impact on the patient's health and maybe life, quality of care is crucial. Health is one of the most significant values in human life. All other facets of our lives also suffer when our health declines. It is a value that allows all individuals to participate fully in society [23]. This helps him accomplish his objectives and see through the daily completion of his previously set responsibilities. Sustaining optimal mental and physical health is a prerequisite for carrying out social tasks in both personal and professional spheres [24].

The World Health Organization (WHO) states that the highest priority in healthcare is quality. Every medical facility works hard to guarantee that the patient is completely satisfied and that the services are of the greatest caliber. The importance of quality is only increasing. It is a crucial factor in determining how a medical facility is positioned in the industry. The progressive standardization and handling of the patient as an individual at the core of the system is the cause of this. It is crucial to treat each person as an individual, paying attention to their needs and the demands they make of the facility. The institutions' rivalry with one another is still intensifying. It is imperative for medical center management to acknowledge that patients have become more cognizant of

their rights and demand the best possible professional treatment [25].

The changes occurring in modern nursing are the reason for the new duties and tasks assigned to nurses. Understanding the patient and using appropriate communication techniques are just as important to quality assurance in medical services as having a state-of-the-art facility, cutting edge machinery, and highly skilled medical personnel. Quality is a process that involves all personnel working in a particular medical facility, rather than a single action. Additionally, it involves choosing the right channels of communication with the patient, particularly when a disease is involved [26]. Since the patient's family is also going through a tough time, the nurse must have the right interpersonal skills. Achieving the intended therapeutic benefits is made easier by selecting the best communication method that is tailored to the patient. Since nurses are essential to the healthcare industry, they play a significant role here [27]. Effective communication has a significant impact on both the betterment of treatment outcomes and patients' happiness with interactions with medical staff. Studies verify that patients demand professional guidance and information that is appropriate for them above anything else from healthcare providers.

of information, but they also require assistance, deference, comprehension, and empathy. The likelihood that a patient will return to a certain facility is determined by the staff's use of proper communication [28, 29].

CONCLUSIONS

The nursing profession is one that is always evolving and assuming new responsibilities. The range of work completed demonstrates how this profession has developed. Providing excellent medical care and safety is a constant. The patient considers aspects like staff interest, safety, and respect in addition to the outcome of the therapy when evaluating the quality of care. Since nurses typically have the initial contact with patients, it is possible to attain a high standard of quality in their treatment thanks to their extensive training. The nursing staff is frequently taken into consideration by patients when evaluating the quality of care received. Adhering to relevant norms and criteria, including those pertaining to safety, efficacy, ethics, accessibility, and professionalism, is what is meant by "quality nursing." Patient requirements must be understood because quality evaluation plays a significant role in determining a medical facility's place in the services market.

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